

Save House Sparrow campaign, by Hirval Foundation.

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INTRODUCTION

Primary information about the case:

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Motivation about the project:

Questioning of a common man about vanishing sparrow from city.

Objective of the project:

Researching the reason of vanishing sparrow.
Designing and developing aids for sparrow survival in city.
Publicity and distribution of artificial nest, feeder and nesting material dispensers among the society.
Satisfying all quarries of layman related with the birds conservation.

CASE PRESENTATION

Conceptualization of the case:

Public's quarries regarding vanishing sparrow are researched. One by one all reasons for vanishing sparrows are checked and verified. Principle reason came forward is, reducing nesting sites in the city deterred the sparrow population. Sparrow is one of the birds who cannot leave its own in the forest or nonhuman habitat. They are evolved to leave along with human civilization; But now, our changing life style, architectural designs of our houses and buildings threatening the survival of sparrow. They need a close and immediate attention to facilitate their survivals in our cities changed scenario.

Working model and scope:

The artificial nest for Indian house sparrow was scientifically designed and experimented. Nest is made from the eco-friendly, reused, chips-ply. Successful designed was fixed at various places in city and trialed. The results were par-excellence; the areas were flourished once again by sparrows. Peoples in the area appreciated the sparrows developing population.

Case effectiveness:

Selected sites for installation of artificial sparrow nest were earlier complained about the vanished sparrows in that area. When we installed the nest around such houses, sparrow came back, started nesting and breeding. Because of this scientific design, post nesting mortality was reduced to zero. Earlier scientific design of artificial nest was quit box like, which was not very attractive and aesthetic design for people, so later the design was changed to increase its aesthetic looks, it has been given the shape of small hut. Thereafter people in society welcomed it. Now some people install this nest on their houses only because of the attractive shape of the nest box, this solves both the purpose.

Management and outcome:

For experimenting with the new scientific design, we have to request and educate the peoples, so they could allow us to experiment around their home. Lots of wood-work has to been done, for that, instead of wasting our time after the carpenters, we our own learned the basic wood working skills and purchased tool required for that. Initially prepared more than 50 different shape sizes, designs of sparrow nest; tested them at different sites, Checked the survival rate in each design, Verified the final design thrice at different locations in two seasons (one year). In monsoon season, regular plywood nest materials were not tolerant to rain water. So, searched for the economical alternative to the plywood with waterproof and termite proof durable properties. In this search come across with the chips-ply in scrap yard (at Satpur MIDC). Most economical, light weight, waterproof, durable,

termite proof and waste material. Ideal for the making such bird nest. To make the nest unbreakable and more secure for sparrow breeding, the hinges were removed and lid was fixed for all the time and the rearrangement of the part of the nest was made to increase its strength when hanged on wall. Locally, nests were distributed by mouth to mouth publicity. The web site was lunched to increase the awareness of the true reason of vanishing sparrow and the perfect solution for calling them back. No self-identity of was revealed during campaigning to reduce the pre- conceptual hazards of Religion, cast, group, and profession. Instead of Highlighting Name of person behind, we only used "Hirval foundation 9422770869" on posters, labels, and web site. Social sites Like, Whatsup, Facebook, Twitter, etc. were used to spread the campaign. Blogging platform was chosen because it's free web hosting, quickly searched in 'Google', and easily updated from anywhere. Paper media Like *Divya Marathi*, *Lokhitderpan*, *Sakal*, highlighted our efforts and camping by taking interviews. For first two year, we provided the facility of nest box installation at the location. This helps us in getting 100% result. Because most of the time people use to take it home, but due to unavailability of installation facility, that nest is just kept as it is in store room, very few were able to install it promptly. Later once people started experiencing the phenomenon of nesting in our artificial nest, they help to spread this message orally in their neighborhood and friends. More and more inquiries when came from Mumbai and Pune, we assigned centers in Pune, Mumbai, Jalgaon. All they are activist of save sparrow campaign.

Economics of this activity:

An initial expense for research and development is our own contribution. Later once the artificial nest design was established, this activity was made self-financing.

Self-financing means, Sale of one nest raise funds for manufacturing another nest. (Actual cost of nest + cost of next nest = distribution cost). We minimized the expenses by developing required skill. Like we learned web designing, we learned poster, labels and brochure designing's, we learned carpeting. Developed in-house workshop for making this nest in quantities, We devote our free times and holidays for making and installing these nest. So we fixed the cost of this each nest as 200Rs. (actual raw material and energy cost is 100Rs. + 100 as charges for making another nest). This cost was fixed in such a way because by selling one nest we get the cost of making another nest. So when people purchase 20 nests we get funds for making 20 extra nests, and like that it goes on increasing. Now it's a self- financing campaign. Last year we distributed 400 nests, and got funds to prepare 800 nests for this year. This system also help a sustainable and steady growth of sparrow population and our save sparrow campaign.

Self-Controlling system:

When people will get satisfied with the sparrow population around their houses, they will stop purchasing this nest and the campaign will also come to an end. So, as the problem of vanishing sparrow will reduce, the supporting aids for solving this problem will also reduce. (A self-control save sparrow campaign). This will help to maintain the species diversity.

Challenges and opportunities:

To fast the process of making more nest we mechanized some steps. To cope-up with the increased raw material cost, we searched for the origin of chips-ply scrap (Industries in Satpur MIDC) and wholesale markets for other accessories, but kept the cost of nest fix 200.Rs from first day of campaign (20 March 2010). The growing awareness and public experiences, increasing demand of this sparrow nest all over the INDIA. It has to be send by transport or courier to the different cities in India which required 50 to 100 Rs. Extra charges. (Solution instead of wasting money on courier we guide those interested people to start similar campaign in their city) To increase effectiveness of this campaign in other cities it has to be installed by some activists in the location there.

Outcome:

During 2009- 10 people in Nashik use to talk that "they don't see any sparrow around". Now nobody says like this, instead they say, "yes we see some sparrow around." We estimated rising of more than 4400 sparrows in Nashik city alone. (Feedback system via "SMS", "Whats'up group" each time nesting occurs). In Pune, around 450 sparrows are developing in these nests. A role model for increasing sparrow population in the city.

Discussion:

When "vanishing sparrow" issue arises, the scientific approach helped us to investigate it properly. One by one, we verified the reasons which come forward during study. Then worked for the solving

the major reason i.e. loss of nesting site, when started installing scientifically developed secure nest, sparrows population started increasing. Proper publicity through internet and social sites and posters, about the above reason of vanishing sparrow, initiated the awareness of installation of artificial nest box. Thus succeed in increasing the sparrow's population in the city within three years, which will steadily increase in subsequent years.

Conclusion:

Public quarries were scientifically challenged and researched. To provide full proof solution, artificial nest box is prepared and distributed by developing volunteers and self-financing system. Problem of vanishing sparrows from the city was worked out and we succeed in calling Indian house sparrow back into the city.

Future plans:

Future research was going on for developing the specific sparrow feeder, and nesting material dispensers. Researching on the public quires of eliminating nuisance of "pigeon" from the city. And calling back "Barn Owl" for control ofRat and mice in food industries and agriculture farms.

Suggestions:

Work on problems scientifically to develop tools to solve the problem, instead of just discussing the issues.

Design and market the campaign systematically (and not for publicity).

Try to Keep all campaigning eco-friendly (check that the campaign in not causing harm to nature by any means)

Instead of asking donations and funds, make a campaign self-financing. It gives freedom for inclusive growth and sustainable development.

Reference:

Improved Design of Nest Box For Indian House Sparrow, *PasserDomesticusIndicus*. Author : S Jawale Chetan, Journal *Bioscience Discovery* I year (2012) I volume = 3 I issue = 1 I pages = 97-100.

Citizen Sparrow, project run by the Bombay Natural History Society. <http://www.citizensparrow.in/index.php?r=site/index>

News paper cutting "Lokahitdarpan, Jalgaon 29 July 2013

एक होती चिमणी. तिचे घर होते...

आज सभोवताली एक नजर फिरवा, कुठे चिमणी किंवा तिचे घरटे दिसते का?

आता आई आपल्या बाळाला भरवतांना चिमणी कोठून दाखवणार? आजी नातवाला चिमणीची गोष्ट तर सांगेल पण चिमणीचे फक्त चित्रच दाखवू शकेल.

चिमण्यांची संख्या इतक्या झपाट्याने का कमी होत आहे?

प्रत्येक प्राण्याला जगण्यासाठी व उत्पत्तीसाठी अन्न व सुरक्षित निवाऱ्याची गरज असते. आपण आपले निवाऱे बांधतांना त्यात चिमणीचे सुद्धा एक घरटे असावे, हे विसरूनच गेलो.

संशोधकांच्या मते कमी होत चाललेल्या घरट्यांमुळे, आपल्या बदललेल्या जीवन शैलीमुळे व रासायनिक कीटकनाशकांच्या अनियंत्रित वापरामुळे चिमणीच्या दोन्ही मूलभूत गरजाच आपण नष्ट करत आहोत.

चला तर मग 'हिरवळ' सोबत...

आपण एक प्रयत्न करू चिमणी वाचविण्याचा प्रत्येक घरी एक घरटं चिमणीचे लावू

अंगणात / गॅलरीत / बाल्कनीत चारा-पाणी देवू

मग आई बाळासाठी गाईल...

"चिव चिव ये
दाणा खा, पाणी पी,
आणि भूरंस उडून जा."

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Inquiry for birds nest & feeder.

Poster Used for spreading awareness among the people.